

Trove researcher consultation report

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1. Background

Since its launch in 2009, Trove has been a leading research portal providing researchers with free access to cultural data from the National Library of Australia (NLA) and hundreds of Australian Partner organisations. Trove is a repository of digitised resources from the NLA and partner organisations, including text-based resources (newspapers, magazines, books, manuscripts) as well as maps and images; a repository of born-digital publications submitted through edeposit; a web archive focused on Australian content; an aggregator of collection metadata from Australian GLAMs, the research sector, government, and community organisations; an aggregator and disambiguation service for information about people and organisations; a discovery service that allows searching across all the digitised, born-digital, and aggregated content; a platform for user engagement and enrichment; and a series of APIs that provide machine-readable access to metadata and digital content. Books, reports, theses, and other media can be accessed, as well as manuscripts, biographies, photographs, diaries, sketches, recorded sound/music, music scores, web archives, maps and artefacts, in addition to reports by Australian universities, and government and non-government bodies and much more. In addition, Trove provides a wealth of data and services for the Australian research community: many researchers who were consulted noted the critical importance of this resource not just for its magnitude, but also for its place as a research entity that is open access, reliable, relatively comprehensive, updated, and easy to use. It is a mainstay of research in Australia today, and a recent issue of *History Australia* outlines its valuable underpinning contributions: see <https://www.tandfonline.com/toc/raha20/18/4>.

Users recognise the difficulty in maintaining Trove at a material and technical level, but they also register the essential research need for it to be sustained, developed, enhanced, and improved. Trove facilitates links to other resources, which can aid in research integration with other national and international infrastructures.

In the 2020 Research Infrastructure Investment Plan the Department of Education Skills and Employment earmarked investment to enable the delivery of a Trove Researcher Platform with new tools for visualisation, entity recognition, transcription and geocoding across Trove content and other corpora. The Trove Researcher Platform forms part of the HASS Research Data Commons and Indigenous Research Capability Program that is being managed by the ARDC. The tools developed as part of the Trove Researcher Platform should sit coherently with the other projects that form that Program.

2. Components of this report

This report is based on discussions and findings that have emerged from consultation with the research community about Trove and how they use it. It aims to inform the nature of a researcher platform, providing:

- An environmental scan
- Suggestions for Trove's enhancements that have emerged

Most researchers recognise that Trove can't solve all research problems, and that incorporating these recommendations may take some time. It has also emerged that many users' requests for improved functionality have been actioned (or, in other cases, the functionality has always been available, if not obvious to users). Some of the discussion with users suggested that guides or instructions may be able to be improved. See Appendix 1 for Mark Raadgever's comprehensive comments on the feedback to Trove from the round tables.

3. Process of consultation

The brief was to consult with researchers about how they use Trove and how they would like to use Trove, in an effort to isolate what the broadly-defined research community would require from a Trove Researcher Platform.

The parameters under which this consultation has taken place are as follows:

- After an Expression-of-Interest process, a researcher panel was appointed, comprising 19 members of the HASS research community from around the country, across different disciplines, and bringing different levels of expertise with Trove (see Appendix 2 for the constitution of this researcher panel). While most members are associated with universities, others represent the GLAM sector or independent researcher groups. Meeting with this researcher panel included leveraging panel members' networks to assist in the wide circulation of the information about the round tables and to canvass responses. It also sought advice on strategies on how a Trove Researcher Platform could be broadly adopted into Australian HASS research activities. It solicited oral and written responses from members to questions about approach, existing work, responses to Trove and Trove functionality, etc. This report relies heavily on their assistance.
- Two virtual public round table discussions were held to ascertain how researchers access and use Trove, and how the needs of HASS researchers could help shape a Trove

researcher platform. Discussion at these round tables was oral, with a question register kept to track researchers' issues, questions, and suggestions

- Consultation with the NLA and ANU through this consultation period
- Consultation with other stakeholders as required.

Discussions with users in the research community provided much in the way of feedback and suggestions (as well as complaints, and recommendations that were out of scope). Less emerged in the way of a definitive vision for a Trove Researcher Platform. With that in mind, this document attempts to consolidate the findings and make some suggestions for progress from here.

4. Environmental scan of Trove use

This scan is based on: responses from round tables; consultation with a range of discipline experts from universities and professional organisations; personal observation; submissions made to the consultation process; discussions with representatives of other ARDC-funded HASS platform projects; and with others who use Trove. The people consulted include researchers (some using basic searches and some with deep knowledge of digital humanities technologies), staff from different government agencies, genealogists, professional historians, armchair researchers, independent researchers, GLAM sector staff (theatre and museum collections staff), university administrators, and tech developers, among others.

Relevant disciplines include history, literature, social sciences, linguistics, theatre, music, cultural studies, media and communication, archaeology, cultural heritage, law, fine art, sociology, Australian studies, Women's studies, and Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander studies.

Inevitably researchers use Trove very differently depending on their discipline(s), the type of question(s) being asked, their level of skill/experience, and the tools with which they have some facility. Some use simple searches while others are expert users of a range of APIs and tools to access and interrogate Trove.

This document is part of a process that endeavours to create a platform to enhance Trove, not necessarily to 'fix' perceived shortcomings there might be in/with Trove and/or Trove data. Having said that, there are multiple 'fixes' that users have recommended and that might be useful for Trove in prioritising plans for the future. While as individual items these recommended improvements may appear to be minor, as a collection of advancements, they can improve researchers' capability and accessibility in searches. It is never possible to answer every question or address every flaw in the system (indeed, in any system), but the items identified here were raised more than once and might inform the development of future enhancements to Trove.

4.1 How researchers use Trove

All manner of researchers (from different disciplines, asking different types of questions, for many different purposes) use Trove to search a very broad range of topics. Some use Trove to begin research processes by ‘getting into the research zone,’ a kind of atmospheric guide to research and the research process. More specifically, this section outlines some of the ways in which Trove is used, with an attempt to group types of uses to an extent. Research questions can be very complex and astutely designed, but they can also be sprawling general searches.

Newspapers

Newspapers are perhaps the predominant type of resource searched, which is perhaps not surprising since many users erroneously think that Trove is newspapers.

Historical research that uses newspapers wholly or in part is crucial to researchers from literary history, history of cultural organisations, family history, and histories of crime. They may be building up comprehensive understandings of single events, topics, or phenomena in the past. In some cases, they wish to examine a particular moment, whereas others fill out the background or context for a specific moment/event (for instance, looking into people or places or images that are relevant to the event, or providing ethnographic or cultural details that are not otherwise recorded). They may follow people or issues. Some users reproduce a full text version of the item(s) found. Other users will conduct more complex searches across time in newspapers to build up a comprehensive understanding of specific phenomena such as the Frontier Wars, or to research the community/people of a specific place, or to examine cultural events, performances, or specific people, events or movements through newspaper coverage. Some researchers examine newspapers to follow language or linguistic use over longer research trajectories.

Trove is used nationally and internationally. An international member of the researcher panel demonstrated, for instance, how she uses Trove not just for education with her students but to investigate European migrants in Australia and to see how European events are covered in Australian papers.

Other types of documents/research materials in Trove

Users access a wide range of other types of Trove documents including government documents, theses, biographies, letters, diaries, government and police gazettes, Indigenous heritage and site histories, conservation management plans, and heritage reports, among many others. In some cases, Trove aids users to find a digitised version of essential material, and in others it is to find where these items are actually housed. It helps users find materials that are not kept in university libraries or library systems. Trove also assists researchers identify and locate library holdings, including books, manuscripts, reports, and theses. Music holdings (sheet music, manuscripts, recordings) are items of interest for some researchers, as are images on a broad range of topics.

More complex research projects

Some researchers, who could be called high frequency users, use Trove far more intensively to produce large scale digital analysis. Broad-scale searches of a topic over time are common (such as examining representation of a particular day across time) in research on the nation and nation formation. Trove aids in the analysis of building responses to cultural or political phenomena across time, and in marking the shifts therein. Public Policy history and analysis require the use of multiple types of Trove data in concert.

Education

Trove contributes to universities' training of undergraduates and higher degree research students, across a range of disciplines.

4.2 How researchers access Trove

Some users use keywords, simple searches, and advanced searches (dates, places, topics, events, among kinds of terms). Others use wikidata, APIs (Trove's own and others), and other tools. These include the Trove APIs, Wandan (wandan.com.au), Zotero (although the link is currently not working which has stalled progress for many users), and the popular GLAM Workbench (built by a HASS researcher and widely used by HASS researchers). The GLAM Workbench tools that were specifically mentioned include QueryPic and Trove Newspaper Harvester. Others use HuNI for analysing or visualising Trove data.

The multiplicity of tools available needs to be recognised: many users deploy these tools as a matter of course. This can be interpreted as a useful outcome because these tools offer multiple ways of interrogating data (or finding different resources, etc.). But it has become clear that the information available about how to use Trove doesn't always facilitate its wide use, nor are platforms or APIs outside of Trove suggested as helpful pathways. That is, users often don't know that the functionality they desire exists on different platforms. Researchers repeatedly noted the need for assistance to better use Trove: this includes a more visible entry to datasets and linked open data, and, almost as important, more skills training and instructions or pathways.

The range of ways in which users access Trove suggests the importance of identifying pathways, especially to ensure that users with more limited skills can gain entry to more of Trove's potential. This is one of the key issues with access: many researchers have limited understanding of what they can do when they turn to the site.

4.3 How researchers could use Trove better, with some proposed enhancements

There are various orders of issues that this environmental scan identifies as important considerations for Trove in the shorter term, whether incorporated into a Trove platform or as stand-alone enhancements.

It is always easier for users to identify what is wrong or what doesn't work like it used to, or to respond to what they can't find, than it is to generate bold new ideas. Nevertheless, the overall ability to request improvements with Trove processes has been identified as limited. It may not actually *be* limited but the perception exists that it is. As noted elsewhere in this report, functionalities deemed not to exist may well exist, but explicit communication of them may not be apparent.

Some general improvements include:

- Improved interface¹ (likely well outside of scope)
- A simple way of notifying the Trove team when problems arise
- The many suggestions beyond these two generic ones can be grouped into the following headings: Searching; Information or What's there/what's coming; OCR; Functionality; Integration; and APIs.

Searching

The search function is an essential entry point. Many responses to consultation focused on problems with searching. This list identifies items that were mentioned more than once. It has also taken account of Mark Raadgever's commentary on what can (currently) be done in Trove, what is likely not possible at this stage, and has been modified in accordance with that information.

- Tips for keyword searches with a view to increasing users' knowledge to conduct more complex searches and search function pointers
- Search function refinements:
 - Make modifying the advanced search clearer, so that experienced users do not automatically 'go back' and lose all their results
 - Add a button for a New Advanced Search
 - Improvements to newspaper searching to allow for the selection of multiple specific items (for example, year, region, article type; or searching the same time space in every year) at one time in newspaper search results
 - Boolean searching: while it is available, users cited its limitations in practice
 - Greater functionality in browse option
 - Returning ability to exclude search results from tags and comments in web interface
- Greater visibility of contents:
 - Improve visibility of non-English language newspapers
 - Images and music are frequently difficult to find; better methods/suggestions for their discoverability would be helpful
 - Online access to more books and documents
- Greater range of contents:

¹ The National Library of Denmark Lab (labs.kb.dk) was noted as a model. See also Library of Congress Laps Newspaper Navigator: an excellent example of data curation, user driven ML training (human-computer loop) and data archaeology: youtu.be/Q_VOq5BMipk.

- Expansion of digitisation of newspapers to include post-war newspapers and more country/rural/regional newspapers.

OCR

While it is wonderful to have access to digitised newspapers, the quality of the reproduction is not always good. Improving the quality of OCR was a frequent request to improve the nature and quality of research. Accuracy was a concern, as was the potential for ‘adaptive OCR’ that learns from corrections so that the same correction doesn’t need to be factored in every time. Alternatively, more recent advancements in newer OCR techniques using unsupervised learning (AI) might be leveraged.

Information for Users or What’s there/what’s coming

As with any resource, there is often a disconnection between what access or functionality exists and what users understand about that access/functionality. It appears that there are gaps between many users’ knowledge of how to use Trove and what it can do. There is an opportunity here for an improvement to instructions, how-to videos, ‘did you know’ prompts, drop-in session, workshops, etc. It is as much the visibility of these aids as their availability. The tracking of the use of such aids to Trove use could also assist NLA staff in managing what appears to be of particular need, popularity, or where a problem exists in access. In further detail, these issues included:

- Respondents struggled to find Trove’s site map
 - They wished to see simply an overview of what’s actually available in a more visible/obvious place (what publications, what years, etc.)
 - This could include how NLA’s own catalogue links to Trove
- They expressed interest in a gaps document, a list that is updated with some regularity
- News sites are difficult to keep updated, but users did suggest the value in such a function
- A digitisation schedule can be found on Trove, but not easily
- A greater range of easy-to-access education tools (printed instructions, videos, occasional workshops on particular topics, occasional virtual drop-in times, etc.) on how to conduct different types of searches. This could include what work-arounds or fixes are known to be useful.

Functionality

The extent of this list indicates the broad range of Trove use, but also the difficulty some users (including experienced ones) have in accessing the data easily. As with the Search section above, this section has been reduced in conjunction with Mark Raadgever’s commentary on what is currently already available.

- Minor functionality improvements
 - Predictive text completion for tags
 - Ability to remove duplicate articles in newspapers automatically
 - Annotate records with custom terms
 - When downloading a page as jpeg or PDF ensure that the image or page is not split in two—although this can be done via Glam Workbench

(<https://glam-workbench.net/trove-newspapers/#save-a-trove-newspaper-article-as-an-image>), built-in to the Trove Newspaper Harvester & the list export tool (<https://glam-workbench.net/trove-lists/#convert-a-trove-list-into-a-csv-file>), and as a command-line tool and software library (https://wragge.github.io/trove_newspaper_images/)

- Remove the inoperative Simple Search button.
- More major functionality enhancements
 - Placename detection and geolocation, in conjunction with ATAP
 - Tools for working with large text corpora—especially Natural Language Processing and Named Entity Recognition, also in conjunction with ATAP
 - Greater attention to the digitisation of video resources, in advance of the 2025 ‘digital cliff’
 - Community-driven Trove wiki; this has operated in the past under the guise of a Trove forum.
 - Interface with similar research resources, principally (but not only) with the English-speaking world: for example, British Newspaper Archive (UK) and Papers Past (NZ)
 - Linked Open Data entity and vocabulary services—building on the value of People Australia in particular.
- Enhance the potential for researchers to add to and supplement data and metadata, and to value-add to Trove, acknowledging that some oversight is required to ensure appropriate practice
 - This includes music pieces to include all participants (essential to allow moral rights to be identified)
 - Tools to support reproducibility
 - Workflow for creating other bespoke research platforms that build on Trove as data archive
 - Feature/emotive tagging music recordings
 - Improved LOD protocol/documentation to promote and facilitate linkage and integration
 - Researcher value-adding could include repositories of research that could benefit others, or ‘User Contributions’ that could enhance data.
- A means of communicating problems back to Trove to:
 - Identify broken links so they can be repaired
 - Notify Trove when missing newspapers are identified so that they may at some stage be added to the database
- It became evident that there are some matters of functionality in and with Trove that are not well understood by users. These might be prioritised in any communications strategy. Among these are:
 - creating subsets of records/items, whether visible just to the user or by others
 - tagging tools
 - OCR corrections

Integration

Integration is of critical concern to users who access Trove for more than a simple search: the means to integrate data sources/resources. Mechanisms to better link data are strongly encouraged.

- Fix Zotero integration
- Better linking to other platforms
- Interface with newspapers in other countries
- Coordinated integration with research-driven platforms (eg GLAM Workbench).

APIs

Many researchers seek to access more of Trove's data in consistent, reliable, well-documented, machine-actionable forms. In many cases this might be via an API, but API access will probably need to be supplemented by large-scale, regularly-updated downloadable datasets (for example, for web archives, or for a complete snapshot of a newspaper corpus). Many researchers reported using the GLAM Workbench because it provides the capability they want to investigate data from multiple sources or in multiple ways, using the Trove API. Consultation suggests that API development is a priority: this includes improvements to Trove's API and, as noted above, better integration with other APIs.

A summary of desirable developments to the API includes:

- Adding people and orgs data to main API
- API for Australian web archive and other significant data archives/collections held by Trove. A search API (or a dataset of extracted features) rather than just the Memento protocol and CDX API of the web archives software would enable researchers to conduct text analytics, network analytics, etc., on the Australian Web Archive and other significant data collections (for instance, where Trove holds not only metadata but the data as well), has massive potential for researchers across the humanities and social sciences
- Make use of IIIF standard APIs for the delivery of images and maps. This would enable the use of the growing ecosystem of IIIF compliant tools for integration, analysis, and annotation
- Online digital exhibition tools: such tools have been developed in the past (see API: <https://github.com/wragge/diy-trove-exhibition>). Some such exhibition functionality through Omeka is available on GLAM Workbench (<https://glam-workbench.net/trove-newspapers/#upload-trove-newspaper-articles-to-omeka-s>)
- Bringing API and web interface back into synchronisation
- Adding metadata about digitised resources other than newspapers to API
- Provide a Write API for annotations
- Relax authentication requirements
- Provide output in CSV format.

4.4 Conclusion to Environmental Scan

There is far more proposed in this scan than could be attended to in short order, but discussions with users illustrated repeatedly just how many users struggle to complete their research. This scan may indicate some pathways for developments that the NLA may wish to incorporate.

The Environmental Scan is also aimed at helping to shape a Trove Researcher Platform with a wider scope than basic fixes. Attention to the API and its development remained a common topic. Users expressed interest in seeing the NLA's public roadmap for API development that encouraged feedback and collaboration. This would enable researchers to plan for future research projects, and to help define needs for possible future NCRIS investments.

Users also sought refinements to their searches, which are frequently larger scale searches. Some wished to do so with the help of an API, others without. Many also wished to create a data set, and then upload that data set as a new resource.

The ARDC is planning an education and skills development component as part of the HASS RDC and Indigenous Research Capability Program, but it became clear through the consultation process that education itself should be a priority in the planning for a Trove Researcher Platform, in terms of:

- Demonstrating what is in Trove, and how users can best deploy Trove
- Providing better skills training for the sector in the use of digital resources.

The first may be more the purview of Trove and the NLA, whereas the second may best be done in conjunction with the university sector. As noted above, many functions that researchers have requested are available already, but the information and instructions are not always easily accessible. Trove staff can often provide an answer/pathway, but that information is not available/visible simply and easily. There was a frequently-expressed need for how-tos: easy-to-follow guides for how to search, etc. In addition, workshops or opportunities to ask questions would be helpful. Further, the function to ask users if what they'd found was what they were looking for ('is this what you wanted? If not, try x').

Finally, the GLAM Workbench, mentioned several times already, offers a wide range of tools that can assist HASS researchers. While embedding it into Trove may not be possible or desirable, there could be considerable scope in stronger links from Trove to the GLAM Workbench, especially in the context of the suggestions offered below. The capability of the GLAM Workbench extends beyond the Trove API in, for example, its screen scraping to retrieve data that is not currently available through the API (for example, lists of digitised journal issues, positional information of newspaper images).

5. Suggestions from the Consultation Process for input into a Trove Researcher Platform

The Environmental Scan may not have produced large-scale thinking about where Trove might develop significantly next, but some possibilities emerged that can be incorporated into the plan for a Trove Researcher Platform.

Researchers frequently expressed the opinion that HASS is not a single entity, suggesting that a single platform for Trove couldn't answer all queries or approaches. It is certainly true that the variety of approaches in even a single HASS discipline is enormous, before the disciplines are aggregated to a group. But there is a perception beyond HASS that we should have long since been able to sort out a direction for our infrastructural needs and demonstrated the ability to use and re-use data/datasets. At one level, HASS researchers will inevitably continue to ask many different questions (and different types of questions) in their research, but at another level, being able to demonstrate at least some integration of research approaches could be advantageous. The range of users and research projects that deploy Trove reinforce that. There can be a value in establishing a means of pooling approaches, at least on some types of searches. This would not preclude other forms of interrogating Trove data or use of Trove tools, but rather it would facilitate a detailed investigation from multiple perspectives of particular subsets. This is not to reduce or exclude, but to demonstrate how HASS researchers might use—and re-use and augment—datasets in a way that enables additions and developments, a factor that may well be helpful in the sector's continued engagement with NCRIS funding.

Trove Community Data Lab

A number of suggestions point to the need for a platform where tools, code and datasets making use of Trove data can be shared, organised, and annotated by researchers. A proposal was submitted to the researcher panel by Conal Tuohy for an innovative approach to a Trove Researcher platform (and its essence is included here with his permission): it requires development of the APIs but could offer much more of the functionality and flexibility that users have explained that they seek. He describes it operating much like a mobile phone's App Store. It would use as its basis a developed version of the Trove API which should reduce any perceived security issues. In any case, it could be possible that such a platform can operate 'for' Trove but 'outside' of Trove. As the 'App Store' metaphor suggests, each of the tools and datasets is semi-independent, loosely coupled to the platform by virtue of being clients of one or more of the Trove APIs.

This proposal offers a Trove in-house storefront for tools and data, a platform that would incorporate the building of a 'collaboration layer' on top of an improved Trove API. On display in

this Trove Community Data Lab platform is in the first order a range of tools with which to explore data. It could incorporate datasets to download, as well as tools and software. There could be room for adding in some community development features, such as discussions, favourites, etc. Such developments could support the growth and expansion of communities of researchers and developers around particular questions, or data types. The apps could also incorporate a great deal of the education and tips for which users of Trove feel the need.

A Trove Community Data Lab could enable the sharing of tools and datasets, environments for running the tools, and options for researchers to tag, favourite, or annotate the tools and datasets. From there it could become an environment where collections focused on particular research questions can coalesce. This tactic provides a community development approach to Trove data and APIs in which there could be more direct connections between Trove and the communities of developers and researchers making use of the data. This approach may open up opportunities to leverage some existing investment through the reuse of other ARDC supported platforms. For instance, the LDaCA-ATAP group will have much technology in place that could be leveraged to create a Researcher Platform in a limited time span.

New tools could be developed as needs arise, based on the findings of others, thus keeping the platform community focused with the collaborative effort of researchers and developers developing tools, examples, and datasets. A Trove Community Data Lab need not be limited by just a few examples of functionality or tools.

This suggestion recognises the dynamic nature of researchers' needs; it also leverages the research community's collective creativity in developing ways to satisfy those needs. The platform would offer a space to carry out a research project but also to engage with new and different tools and to share what is possible with them. It also facilitates a use and reuse approach to data.

Tuohy proposes that the platform be shaped as/by app-hosting websites. This would leverage the growth in "online development environments (ODEs)" which take advantage of "fiddles, notebooks, and other web apps [that] are the kinds of tools which the Project should be aiming to curate, organise, and support." He explains that "that organising these apps (rather than hosting them) is the key missing piece of the puzzle." This type of response to platform generation would entail the establishment of an app registry, including Trove-specific code libraries in the app registry, and running customisable app-hosting platforms where there is clear benefit to researchers. There would be a larger capability for integration with other resources.

There are multiple benefits from such an approach. It keeps research open and collaborative. It offers a structured way of learning about different tools and methods for using Trove data and **therefore broader accessibility to more researchers**. It facilitates the larger development of new tools and new ways of conducting large-scale research projects in and with Trove. It offers the capacity for the enhanced use of Trove by researchers, a better development of user

communities and user co-creation, and a better interaction between researchers and Trove. It responds to users' stated need for more information on how to capture the data they seek, a wider range of tools and functionality, and a better comparability of skills among and between users. It has the potential to address many of the difficulties users have with Trove while also increasing the possibility of in-depth, significant, and collaborative research with Trove and Trove resources.

A Trove Community Data Lab approach could assist with the generation of focused platform(s) of tools and collection subsets for open groups of researchers. To provide an example of how the 'collaboration layer' described above might actually work in practice, researchers with a shared interest or focus could curate/create/collect a set of tools and datasets within the larger platform and embed them within their own set of discussions, documentation and annotations. These could have their own landing page but still be part of the broader platform. Linked access to a more limited pool of resources might enhance search functions and skills for a broad cross-section of researchers, while also developing depth in some topics or approaches or tools. One means of exploring the extent of the collections in the Australian context, while also producing significant new research, is to help generate several mini-platforms that group certain types of collections and tools for investigation in multiple ways by researchers from many disciplines. A mini-platform or focused platform could incorporate sophisticated search tools, language interrogation, visualisation, mapping and placenames and geolocation, and images. It could provide linked data for visualisation via knowledge graphs and network analysis that would provide new insights into Australian society. It would need to be open to others complementing data, while not compromising what has already been completed. It would house datasets which could be created, developed, returned to, and used by others, whether to test, interrogate differently, or to add to with new data. It could have, in conjunction, a form of exhibition or teaching component to it as well. It would be a series of sets and subsets of data that still could include integration with resources beyond itself. The mini-platforms could themselves be linked and could spark new examples.

The pooling and reuse of a collection of Trove data and data types could be a user-generated data access and storage platform to share results of researcher inquiry across a broad range of GLAM materials. It also facilitates exploration of broader questions about discoverability and research replication. Not only could it use and reuse data, it could demonstrate the use and reuse of tools in ways that other researchers could adopt for separate investigations. Some standardisation would be required (how different classes of data function within the information architecture of Trove), but not in the order of generating new standardised schemata.

It could provide a conglomeration of data in ways that may well be useful in themselves and to build further research on, across multiple disciplines and resources. Some establishment of standard practices across GLAM sectors could be incorporated.

It would help delimit some research parameters while enabling a deeper analysis of what is gathered in a findable/searchable way. It would generate a sandbox of sorts that would allow other data to be contributed. This type of data commons with standardised indexing would include metadata and provide a means of continuous feeding in. A grouping of like resources cannot cover all researchers' needs, but it could provide a valuable, more consolidated research collection.

Who would be included? Which data? What tools? Ideally, this would depend on a broad collection of researchers incorporated. These platforms might be shaped initially by a group of researchers but would be fundamentally as open access as other aspects of Trove. Some examples of focus points for topics could include:

- Indigenous data sets and research questions related to Indigenous peoples and research themes. While the ARDC's Supporting Indigenous Research Capability project (led by the University of Melbourne) is working on capacity building and data governance, the integration of actual data sets by and about Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples would be valuable
- Temporal event-based topics such as pre-Federation resources or the world wars (as examples of temporal/event driven topics)
- Gender in Australia (especially in the context of the recent Library of Congress decision to cease recording gender in personal name authorities)
- Sunsetting or completed digital humanities projects: a humanities data repository to preserve sunsetted projects. It is a different type of archiving and preserving project, but the physical parallel would be their manuscript or other archival collections. An aggregator of data repositories would be useful in its own right, let alone in potential exploration across them.

There are any number of appropriate examples to begin generating mini-platforms. These are simply initial suggestions to offer several different ideas of both critical weight and collaborative research benefit.

Discussions with the research community suggested that there are two orders of users: those who use simple search tools and those who are more sophisticated users. To move some of the first group to the second, researchers need to see how to use the various tools available. A possibility is an overview of completed projects or notional projects with a description of the pathways to completion with and through Trove. This would have an added benefit of expanding the reach of subsets of research/scholarship across the Australian HASS community.

Location of an App Store Platform approach within the NLA

The National Library has noted that an app store approach presents security issues, stating:

The National Library appreciates the desire from the research community for a platform to develop, store and make accessible researcher-created and researcher-managed tools. However, this is not achievable as a component of the National Library's own systems, including but not limited to Trove, within the proposed timeframe or cost envelope. As an APS agency, the National Library of Australia must assure the security compliance of all code and applications hosted on its domain, an endeavour which is becoming increasingly challenging. To securely and effectively host such a platform would require significant re-architecting of existing platforms, and significant ongoing costs to manage.

Such a platform could, however, be built outside Trove and the NLA. The potential benefit of a location outside Trove is that it could then begin to incorporate APIs and additional resources to service a wider GLAM sector and ATAP, among other ARDC platforms.

Wish-list for the future

Other matters that arose in discussions but that can't easily be accommodated in the sections above include the following:

- Provide historical statistics on Trove resources (as were available in the past)
- Semantic catalogue which can link to other institutions and to citizen contributors. This is useful to enable access to the variety of GLAM resources in the country
- Better integration of video
- Better ability to look towards the accommodation of 3D recordings such as photogrammetry images and laser scan point clouds of place and objects
- Scope for a text-to-speech function for those with visibility or learning difficulties
- Greater ability to link to international resources
- An integrated national project of an Historical Register of The Australian People, partnering with state and territory registries to provide major health, demographic, human geographic data that could incorporate geo-spatial tagging of vital registrations can track movement, social mobility, settling, effects of droughts and economic busts and booms, etc.
- Trove is text focused, even if there is a broad range of music, photographic, visual and manuscript-based materials collected by the NLA and available through Trove (both NLA held and provided via links to other resources). In an attempt to develop other approaches, other users, other research questions and other outputs, attention to non-text-based resources and tools could be useful. It would be desirable for searches that move beyond the text based, and a means of exploring the data in pictorial (or non-text based) ways. This argument is also important for creative arts and visual cultures researchers who would appreciate increased discoverability

of non-textual holdings such as images, music scores, audio and video could be considered. A potential direction to produce this is the leveraging of AI machine learning technologies to produce associated data or on-the-fly searching, for example music notation encoding, image recognition, and audio tagging/transcription.

6. Conclusion

A Trove Researcher Platform could ideally facilitate a richer and deeper engagement with Trove data, while relying on different tools and resources, in a shared research environment. The opportunity exists to develop a researcher platform that offers a coherent vision involving data, tools and training.

The engagement with a cross-section of the HASS research community that sits behind this report envisages Trove remaining not just fit for purpose but a leading resource that drives innovative research in Australia. There is an enormous range of ways in which researchers use Trove, and ways in which the research community works with each other to enhance the benefits of data gathering, research in and around Trove. Trove has led the world in making available the wealth of data that it does, but without a push for greater advances and functionality, Australia could be left behind.

6. APPENDIX ONE

Trove response to researcher feedback

Feedback from Roundtables

Suggestion/Feedback	Trove response
URLs for Newspaper articles in the API are not the same as the current page URLs or PIs	Added to the list of API Bugs
Accuracy of Trove entries: Link rot is a thing - so work with providers to ensure content is accurate, and links to local resources goes to where it's supposed to	Limited by data providers including the correct links and updating us when these are updated.
Ability for api to access "First Nations" content as per online search (a new zone?).	Can be achieved using <i>first_australians_ind:y</i> or <i>cultural_sensitivity:y</i> in an API query string Added to list of help updates
Distinction of temporal metadata between: the time extent of the subject described, when the item was published, and when the metadata was last updated (and all needs to be searchable (used in filters) e.g. to support getting new or changed content)	Described in the Trove help https://trove.nla.gov.au/help/searching/constructing-complex-search-query https://trove.nla.gov.au/constructing-search-query-v2 https://trove.nla.gov.au/about/create-something/using-api/api-technical-guide#list-of-supported-indices
A strong commitment that work ids will be stable i.e. can function as persistent IDs.	Work IDs are persistent except where an item is deleted and re-loaded at a much later date, or an individual record is moved out of a work (the work ID of the original work will remain the same, and the moved record will create a new work ID)
Help providers move towards using controlled vocabularies and standardised ways of describing their content (like Austlang).	AustLang codes are covered in the help https://trove.nla.gov.au/austlang-codes Other controlled vocabularies can be added to the help and guidance provided, however we cannot control how providers use these vocabularies.

<p>Searching for bibliographic items (e.g. articles, books, chapters, manuscripts) often seems less satisfactory in Trove than eg in NLA or a Union catalogue</p>	<p>These are hard to quantify without specific examples.</p> <p>Help on generating a search query, which could mitigate these issues, is covered in the help on constructing search queries above.</p>
<p>Can corrections be used as training data for Machine Learning and then reapplied to Trove's data in a systematic way</p>	<p>Bulk Export functionality is under investigation.</p> <p>Integrating any machine learning back into Trove's data has significant processing and resourcing implications.</p>
<p>Provide other relevant keyword searches related to your search</p>	<p>This is tricky to implement as what could be relevant to one user may be completely irrelevant to another user.</p> <p>Some investigation into a 'did you mean' function has been completed historically, however, at the time the balance between resourcing and perceived value was not positive.</p> <p>This will be raised as something to be investigated again as it may be more achievable with advances in the core technologies used by Trove.</p>
<p>Allow a Trove "list" to be automatically ordered by historical date – and kept ordered as new articles are added.</p>	<p>This will be raised as a potential for Trove development</p>
<p>A means to correct erroneous Titles in newspaper articles</p>	<p>This has been investigated historically, however could not be implemented at that time.</p> <p>This functionality will be raised as something to be investigated again.</p>
<p>Reinstate former tickbox to restrict newspaper search to "Title and first four lines</p>	<p>This functionality will be raised as something to be re-instated in future.</p> <p>Short term this is achievable using the <i>headingsAuthorAbstract</i> index. Added to the list of help updates</p>
<p>"Predictive completion" options when users tag items, to encourage re-use of existing popular tags for a particular topic rather than users typing</p>	<p>This will be raised as a potential for Trove development</p>

<p>out their own tag. Would improve coherence of tags rather than many disparate tags with similar meaning.</p>	
<p>Limited newspaper coverage hampers research in particular jurisdictions or perspectives.</p>	<p>Newspaper coverage is limited by funding available for digitisation of these newspapers as well as availability of source material and rights restrictions.</p>
<p>Ability to 'add on' rather than refine search e.g. searching first on name, then add keyword, then add place, in order capture idiosyncrasies of reporting</p>	<p>This is currently possible. In a simple search you can add the keywords into the search bar, with an advanced search, selecting the 'show advanced search' link after the original search has completed allows you to refine the search using the advanced search form.</p> <p>This will be added as a help update</p>
<p>Improve metadata on music performers and performances, not just performers</p>	<p>This requires a source of this data to be available for harvesting into Trove</p>
<p>Implement search of music notation in digitised holdings (i.e. via Optical music recognition and encoded symbols, e.g. MEI, MusicXML)</p>	<p>This is tricky to implement in a text-based system such as Trove.</p> <p>Trove is capable of indexing the content of an item that is linked to, so anything that is stored in these formats may be searchable as long as it is stored in a filetype that Trove is able to index, and we are given the necessary information to index these items.</p>
<p>Semantic catalogue which can link to other institutions and to citizen contributors</p> <p>Integrating more closely with Wikidata would provide ways to import Trove data and then Trove and anyone else having access to all the related data in Wikidata</p>	<p>Would require significant changes to Trove's underlying infrastructure to support.</p>
<p>Providing the capability for researchers/projects to identify project specific metadata (with research specific taxonomies) to Trove records might mitigate the requirement for small scale projects to build their own systems.</p>	<p>This is already achievable using Trove tags. If wanting to specify the taxonomy, tag prefixes can be used.</p>

	Collection features could also be used to support researchers/projects with maintaining a Trove data set and having this available into the future.
Occasionally I find newspaper articles referenced in other texts and they aren't available on Trove - could there be a way to report missing Newspapers so they can be found and added to the database?	Not all Australian newspapers are digitised in Trove, and although most Australian newspapers have holdings, we do not know for certain which newspapers have full holdings. Newspapers are digitised as part of the Trove partnerships process, and can have a long lead time as they are sourced and processed.
Further to above, easily visible list of which newspapers are being/going to be digitised	It is possible to see which newspapers have been digitised, and are in the process of being digitised at https://trove.nla.gov.au/newspaper/about , although filtering just those that are in process is tricky. A list of newspapers that were in the pipeline was maintained historically, however, there were some difficulties in maintaining this due to the list changing depending on whether the material was available. Recorded as something for further investigation
Some missing newspaper articles and content is held in smaller repositories i.e. historical societies etc. could there be a way to encourage those bodies to contribute to trove?	There is an ongoing process that has been working with these smaller organisations to encourage them to contribute their records to Trove. Many such organisations do already contribute their data, and have funded digitisation of their local newspapers
A great addition for those interested in large-scale analysis would be embedding Tim Sherratt's GLAM Workbench tools in the Trove site as part of a suite of tools to assist and innovate research - and teaching!	IT Security and other concerns may not permit embedding of these tools into Trove. It may be possible to include links out in the Trove help, or through the Researcher portal. Recorded for further investigation
Work with domain experts in the Research sector to plan and develop the Trove collection (coverage of all high value items surely a worthwhile aim?). It would be great to see Trove aim to include all important domain portals/databases, and to discuss at what level of	This is a strategic issue and Trove is already working with many of the major Australian institutions to include their collections in Trove.

<p>aggregation data could be sourced and linked. Linkage will need agreed conventions for giving things stable identifiers (in itself, such agreement would be a huge advance; this is a data governance issue).</p>	
<p>Set up a representative Users' Panel to advise on strategic direction and priorities</p>	<p>Trove partners have the Trove Strategic Advisory Committee - https://trove.nla.gov.au/partners/trove-strategic-advisory-committee - to provide input on the direction of Trove</p>
<p>A user friendly API service or similar Improved APIs</p>	<p>Technical work on enhancing the Trove API has been identified for further investigation.</p>
<p>More transparency around technical architecture Not really a tool, but it would be useful to have a published technical architecture that shows all the parts of Trove (collections, harvesting etc.) and where the API sits (maybe there is one we have missed?)</p>	<p>Trove's technical architecture and workflows are available in the Trove help - https://trove.nla.gov.au/about/what-trove/technical-ecosystem, with the systems and data flow diagram specifically at https://trove.nla.gov.au/sites/default/files/attachments/2020-06/Trove%20systems%20and%20data%20flows%20diagram.pdf</p>
<p>Workbench to support researchers to create Trove based research projects. Support creation of project specific metadata fields configurable to use research specific (and project specific) taxonomies. Support identification of project metadata with Trove records. Support export of data (Trove and custom metadata) for analysis and visualisation in external platforms</p>	<p>Data contributed to Trove is stored in one of three metadata formats, MARCXML, Dublin Core or EAC-CPF.</p> <p>Project metadata in Trove records can be supported through the use of Tags, which can also be exported through the Trove API</p> <p>Changing Trove to support custom metadata fields for individual researchers is not technically feasible, particularly as they can use Tags to achieve these same goals.</p>
<p>I'm interested in the potential for Trove to develop a user-generated data access and storage platform to share results of researcher inquiry in eg manuscripts and archives, as well as oral histories and the whole range of GLAM type materials</p>	<p>This is something that may be achievable, although the exact process would need some ironing out.</p> <p>Currently the National Library is managing the National eDeposit Scheme, which provides publishers with the ability to submit their items</p>

<p>Is the question whether the NLA has a role to play (or interest) in archiving and preserving end of project digital research outputs, with these things to be accessible through Trove just the way any other NLA collections are? The physical parallel would be their manuscript or other archival collections. (State Libraries and other suitable archives (University collections?) could also archive and preserve these archives, with discoverability through Trove with good integration?)</p> <p>Research and policy Reports continue to be a major form of publication not collected and managed at a national scale. APO.org.au plays a key role in this but needs national focus working with NLA/Trove</p>	<p>for Legal Deposit, and these items then become available through Trove.</p> <p>It sounds like this would be a similar process to NED, but would require strategic decisions to be made.</p>
<p>Another idea - should some aggregator of data repositories (Research Data Australia?) be searchable through Trove?</p>	<p>RDA is currently harvested into Trove, however, it does appear that the feed Trove is using to harvest this content may need some work as we cannot currently harvest the full data corpus.</p>

Feedback through researcher panel

<p>Trove might become Australia's one-stop shop for aggregated research output metadata, providing greater searchability/discoverability of institutional repositories and their deep archives</p>	<p>This can only work through the research institutions providing their data to Trove through automated processes that are already set up. As mentioned by Jason in reference to RENE</p>
<p>Increased discoverability of non-textual holdings such as images, music scores, audio and video could be considered in terms of leveraging unsupervised machine learning technologies to produce associated data or on-the-fly searching</p>	<p>There are some ethical and privacy aspects that would need to be considered here, particularly in relation to images and video.</p> <p>There is also some question about the best way that this could be achieved, whether it is through an external API or managed internally. Both have risks and costs associated with them</p>
<p>The accuracy and reliability of the search results have been so poor that I have to manually check</p>	<p>Searching full text content, particularly that produced by OCR, is always going to create false</p>

<p>each text file for relevance and then correct relevant texts in Trove before compiling a final 'clean' dataset. This makes it impossible to do large scale linguistic studies.</p>	<p>positives according to the desires of the researcher.</p> <p>In the case of the example fulltext:"Australia Day"~0 all items reviewed include the search terms consecutive to each other, as entered. This is not inaccurate, it is simply that the text includes the search terms and does not match the researcher's expectations. When sorted by relevance all articles on the first page of results do have reference to Australia Day as an event.</p>
<p>I would be interested to know whether punctuation can also be accounted for between words?</p>	<p>This is not technically possible to achieve without having a significant impact on the discoverability of content. OCR content often contains incorrectly added punctuation which would result in these searches returning no results</p>
<p>It would be useful to ask Trove what materials they based the OCR work on – whether they were scanning old microfilm (probably) or the original documents?</p>	<p>Both Microfilm and Original documents are used depending on availability https://trove.nla.gov.au/partners/partner-service/digitisation-services/digitisation-process</p> <p>Newspapers have typically been scanned from microfilm for reasons of efficiency. If we were scanning only from hard copy (assuming that the hard copy is available and in a condition suitable for scanning) we would have significantly fewer pages digitised. With no guarantee of significantly improved OCR accuracy.</p>
<p>At the moment, the search engine allows for date searches from X to Y only. I would like to be able to search, for example, from 01 Jan to 31 March for every year, in one search hit.</p>	<p>Date searches use a date stamp within the record to be able to search dates as a range.</p> <p>Searching in the suggested fashion is not technically feasible due to the strain that it would put on Trove's resources (it is the equivalent of running over 200 OR statements).</p>
<p>Ongoing digitisation of postwar newspapers</p> <p>Increase the number of country/rural/regional newspapers that are currently digitised</p>	<p>Digitisation of newspapers proceeds in conjunction with partners, and is continuing.</p> <p>Postwar newspapers (assuming that they mean post-WW2) are trickier due to copyright</p>

	restrictions meaning that anything after 1954 requires clearance.
More 'translation' into proper script - many documents are still illegible and turn up false results in searches because the search engine discerns words that aren't actually there.	This is why we provide the ability for people to correct the text. Unfortunately quality of source material is part of the issue here.
Clearer images (pictures) from newspapers. Better quality could be achieved.	This is an artifact of digitising the newspapers for access, and digitising from Microfilm. To get the best quality images from newspapers it is better to scan them individually so that the appropriate adjustments can be made.
'Outreach' to small museums and historical societies that hold difficult-to-access newspapers and documents, and either train them up in uploading their materials, or send out persons who can.	<p>Outreach to small museums and historical societies is ongoing. Many collections are already available through Trove, although these will be in categories other than newspapers.</p> <p>A proportion of newspapers available in Trove have been digitised in partnership with historical societies.</p> <p>Adding newspapers to the digitised newspapers zone can only be done through following the current digitisation workflow, and it is not possible to upload items on an ad-hoc basis.</p> <p>The ability for these organisations to upload items directly to Trove could be considered alongside providing researchers with the same ability.</p>
Combining with museum/gallery databases, and private collections, to achieve a more comprehensive span of images on any given topic.	Trove currently does do this with our Trove Partners program. We are limited by what is available from these partners, and their technical capabilities to work with us.
Online access to more books and documents	Trove is working to provide access to online access through our partners as well as NLA digitisation programs.
A simple way of adding the capacity to match the "case" in search terms so that it is easier to	As with adding punctuation to searches this increases the likelihood that a relevant article will not be returned.

<p>distinguish between surnames and common nouns (Carter, Butcher versus carter, butcher etc.)</p>	<p>Other search strategies can be used to artificially create this limit see https://trove.nla.gov.au/constructing-search-query-v2 or https://trove.nla.gov.au/help/searching/constructing-complex-search-query</p>
<p>Add the function of being allowed to determine if the results will provide hits with similar words (or whole or partial words). I.e. search for “transfer of land” returns over 81,000 results, many of which include the word “landed”</p>	<p>Covered in the search help, link above</p>
<p>When a user is logged in, could they tick an option to only see articles they have not tagged or edited?</p>	<p>Added to list of items to be investigated. May not be technically feasible.</p>
<p>Ability to download and print a list of all articles a user has tagged and/or edited with a specific search term and/or a list of those not tagged or edited?</p>	<p>Added to list of items to be investigated. May not be technically feasible</p>
<p>Ability for users to add notes to newspaper articles that correct information, i.e. cite a death certificate to alert the reader that a date of death in a newspaper is actually incorrect</p>	<p>This functionality already exists in Trove as Notes https://trove.nla.gov.au/help/become-voluntrove/notes</p>
<p>OCR errors can be useful to find new search terms. For example, the OCR for an article on a building might have the word ‘bluestono’. If one then searches within TROV the term ‘Coburg bluestono’ often new results can be found. Is there a way that Trove editing volunteers could warn other users of some of the common errors to assist their searching?</p>	<p>Flagged for possible inclusion in a help update.</p>
<p>Can the highlighted keywords from the original search show up in the raw text for editing?</p>	<p>As the text edit function opens text boxes this is not technically possible.</p> <p>Using the mouseover edit icon rather than the ‘match text’ button allows for specific lines to be edited. See https://trove.nla.gov.au/help/become-voluntrove/text-correction</p>

<p>Boolean searching needs to work, especially 'xxx' AND 'xxx', "xxx' NOT 'xxx', Build* for building, builder, etc.</p>	<p>All of these functions work. See previous links on constructing a search.</p>
<p>When downloading a page as jpeg or PDF ensure that the image or page is NOT splits in two (because this makes this tool useless if the image is to be reproduced articles/reports</p>	<p>If downloading the entire page it should not be split.</p> <p>Downloading individual articles requires extracting the article from the page and more information can be found at https://trove.nla.gov.au/help/using-trove/downloading#newspapers-amp-gazettes</p> <p>Reviewing article downloads has been added for investigation</p>
<p>The search by phrase function seems to work exactly the same as 'any or all of these words'. The relevance sorting does not collect the actual phrase results at the beginning of the results, but rather simply a collection of results containing some or all of the words. Adding inverted commas to the phrase gives a slightly different result, but there is no indication that the results reflect all appearances of the phrase.</p>	<p>There was a bug with 'search by phrase' on the Trove advanced search page which was fixed in May (after the document was created).</p> <p>If this behaviour continues we will need specific examples to review.</p>
<p>Search buttons: Make modifying the advanced search clearer, so that experienced users do not automatically 'go back' and lose all their results; Add a button for a New Advanced Search; Remove the inoperative Simple Search button.</p>	<p>This has been added to the list of items for investigation.</p>
<p>Separate pictures (images) from Trove altogether on their own specific site</p>	<p>This is unlikely as it goes back to a situation where many different services need to be maintained.</p>
<p>Is there any scope for a text-to-speech function for those with visibility or learning difficulties (such as dyslexia)?</p>	<p>Trove has been designed to work with screen readers, and all major browser have text-to-speech plugins that can be installed. Because of this, this functionality is unlikely to be added to Trove directly.</p>

<p>Allowing the user to structure their workspace. To order things in a way that suits the user. I don't like lumping maps and images as a search category together for example and I'd rather reorder the way the category results appear so that books come first.</p>	<p>Allowing users to develop their own search groupings is not technically possible.</p> <p>Allowing users to change the order of their categories has been added for to the list for investigation. It may not be technically possible.</p>
<p>And as I say I'd like to be able to be make some slight changes to the way citations appear [particularly newspapers] -</p> <p>Unlike 'newspapers and gazettes', the citations provided for 'magazines and newsletters' are not tailored to the article or even the issue being consulted</p>	<p>Citations in Trove are generated based on information contained within the individual records being added to specific fields.</p> <p>Changing the way that they are generated for newspapers would require significant change to the underlying data structures.</p> <p>A review of generated citations has been added as something to be investigated</p>
<p>Their category headings don't even make sense; why reproduce the same information in two categories - the image is also in the images category.</p>	<p>Category headings were developed with consultation with end users. Information about categories can be found https://trove.nla.gov.au/help/categories</p> <p>Items may appear in two separate categories because Trove uses data included in individual records to determine which category they belong in. Rather than using a first category only process Trove includes items in all relevant categories to ensure that people searching single categories only can find what they are looking for.</p>
<p>Perhaps 'quick search' could be a bit more sophisticated so that we don't have to always resort to advanced search for most searches. If searching for two words it could assume those two words are meant to be together and produce results for those two (or three or whatever) words together first. To limit the search to something published/produced in a particular year or years, you could add the year to the search lines. If it's a range of years, say 1960-1970 it would bring results for anything published/produced from 1960 to 1970.</p>	<p>See search help.</p> <p>Although these behaviours may make it easier for the individual who suggested this, they are likely to confuse other users. Particularly the suggestion on date searching, where users may be searching for a specific mention of a date, not just items published in that year.</p> <p>When searching for two or more individual search terms the relevance ranking algorithm does boost items where the words have closer proximity, however it will not always display these first due to other factors that influence relevance,</p>

	including which field the matching search terms appear in and the length of the document.
If you're in newspapers and you've got an exact date of a paper you want to look at it'd be nice to just give that exact date in the simple search rather than have to use advanced search.	This functionality will be added to the list of items to be reviewed.
The newspaper search box which used to respond to me entering in a search term alongside a date and/or newspaper name and ask me if I am searching for that term in a particular newspaper and/or on a particular date.	Restoring this functionality will be added to the list of items to be reviewed.
The magazines and newsletters search is clunky. There are too many steps from the search results screen, to viewing the relevant article. Once an item is selected you then have to click on the 'read' button which you would think would take you to the item, but instead you then need to click further on 'View at Trove Digital Library' (which strangely is not presented as a 'button') before accessing the item.	<p>The 'Read' button opens a list of links as in many cases we have more than one source of a given item.</p> <p>This functionality has been added to the list for review for where there is only a single link to the item.</p>
It would be useful if researchers were able to alter the default settings for the sizes of images being downloaded. For the work that I am doing, I rarely find that the automatic setting of 'medium' produces an image of adequate size and would prefer to be able to set the default at 'large'.	This may be something that can be added to the user profiles. Added for review.
Better aggregate data to assess newspaper article content	<p>Currently it is possible to review all newspapers that are currently in the system at https://trove.nla.gov.au/newspaper/about</p> <p>It may be possible to provide better/different aggregate data, however more information is required on what would be suitable.</p>
Automated multiple searches and save functions, e.g. a tool that could search and filter name, then a date and place, only needing verification at the end	<p>More information on how this would work and what sort of data would be expected is required.</p> <p>As this is doable using scripting of the API it may be achievable, however further information is needed to ensure that it isn't taken in completely the wrong direction</p>

<p>Geo-mapping visualisation to show the distribution of news beyond chronological fluctuations -, e.g., Melbourne dailies, Victoria, national</p>	<p>Some work has been done historically on geomapping the data in Trove by various API users.</p> <p>Added as something to be investigated further, although it may be something where the work has already been completed and it's appropriate for a link to be provided out from Trove</p> <p>Data regarding state of publication and coverage is available in Trove, so it is reasonable that we could provide better access to this data.</p>
<p>Better awareness of new additions to Trove, e.g. news site is not up to date.</p>	<p>This is tricky to manage as Trove is constantly having new data added. The existing news page is for Trove events, blogs and similar, not intended to provide updates of new content that is added to Trove.</p> <p>If we restrict this to only newspapers and gazettes it may be possible to do something. Added to list of things for future investigation.</p>
<p>Operability with Zotero requires attention since the last update, e.g. it saves digitised magazines as whole pdf rather than the precise page, and Zotero stores the reference details for these as generic webpages</p>	<p>This may be related to the differences between how digitised magazines and digitised newspapers are stored and managed within Trove's ecosystem.</p> <p>This has been flagged for further investigation.</p>
<p>There is a notable difference between academics and public/activist/practitioner search results. That may be informed by the questions asked (or training), but worth noting.</p>	<p>This comment indicates that there is space to provide training specifically for researchers that can be tailored to their requirements. Most of the existing help in Trove is targeted at general users who do not necessarily need to access complex functionality.</p>
<p>Many researchers use the APIs (e.g. Tim Sherratt's gia tools). However, this can produce issues with reproducibility as an API call is not against a stable data set. Items may come (and go?) and text is corrected (e.g. the newspaper archive), so queries are not guaranteed to produce the same result.</p>	<p>This is an artifact of the frequently updated nature of Trove.</p> <p>It suggests that there may be a desire for researchers to be able to generate a data set from Trove, that can then be stored and made available to download for reproducibility. The risk with this approach is that the researcher may miss new</p>

<p>The LDaCA approach we have discussed would allow for Trove data to be packaged as a stand-alone dataset in Research Object Crate format that can be stored in our infrastructure for re-use so that researchers can work against a stable dataset and compare results.</p>	<p>and updated data as it comes in.</p> <p>Added to list of items for further investigation</p>
<p>Tools and support for tagging/labelling items/collections in Trove to improve data quality (e.g. tagging Indigenous content with AustLang codes). There has been minor support of this in the past. Tagging could be in degrees of authority to support different qualities of research; general public, Trove staff, and tags that have been approved by relevant community authorities, especially for Indigenous content. This could be facilitated by discovery and tagging interfaces (extend Wandan to include tagging features for example), and also requires staffing at Trove (e.g. staff at Trove with knowledge of Indigenous languages) to support discovery. Discovery workshops/tagging training could be conducted nationally to encourage tagging.</p>	<p>Tags can be used both haphazardly and in a controlled fashion.</p> <p>It is possible to use the existing tag system to perform all of this work, although they won't be separated by perceived authority</p> <p>This point does raise that training in how to tag in a targeted and consistent manner may be worthwhile to develop as part of a broader researcher help.</p>
<p>Services for researchers to request Trove correct OCR output (would require staffing capacity). Tools/interfaces for researchers to make their own corrections to the OCR, which would update the original content. This is value-add type of tool.</p>	<p>OCR content can already be corrected through the Trove interface. A recent update to Trove extended this to Books and Journals, not just newspapers.</p> <p>Further information may be required to fully understand what is being requested here</p>
<p>Offer a range of services throughout the research lifecycle: pre-research engagement (examples, advice and even dedicated librarian support), research engagement (access to analytics tools, dedicated data science work) post-research tools (support dissemination and integrate findings into collections). This could be done in an integrated virtual environment (a Trove Labs model).</p>	<p>Analytics and post-research tools are covered by some of the previous points, and will be investigated.</p> <p>The pre-research engagement can be achieved through the Trove contact form (for advice on using Trove) and/or the National Library's Ask a Librarian service.</p> <p>Data science work requires a level of expertise that is not currently in the Trove team</p>
<p>Improve the quality of collections for research purposes by offering ways to "ground truth" them by opening them up to transcription, annotation</p>	<p>Further information is required for this, some aspects may already be in Trove to some degree</p>

<p>and crowdsourcing. Researchers who can see this annex materials but also communicate with community members who produces them can better situate their research in context.</p>	
<p>Community-driven tools: Trove is both an archive and an aggregator of other archives - which is an essential function to have - but it is centrally controlled. Communities do not have access to it to change it, contest content etc. There is another type of system which is popular with some communities where things are structure more like an encyclopaedia or a wiki that allow for connections to be made between items in collections and for people to tell their own stories</p>	<p>Trove’s core is metadata supplied by partner organisations to aid in discovery of their collections. As such, beyond allowing annotations to records, it is unlikely that users will be given the ability to make changes to Trove content within Trove itself. Downloading material from Trove, interacting with it, and uploading that material as new data, however, is something that can be investigated.</p> <p>Connecting items for people to tell stories can be achieved to some degree by the use of Trove lists, however further investigation of ways for users to connect items in Trove has been added as something to be looked at.</p>
<p>Integrating with historical gazetteer would improve the geospatial faceted search of Trove.</p>	<p>This has been added to items for further investigation. Trove currently uses Named Entity Recognition and gazetteer data in addition to bibliographic metadata to populate the geospatial faceted search</p>
<p>Integrating with ALA’s DigiVol would facilitate crowdsourcing (but perhaps it does already in some limited way?).</p>	<p>Trove does not currently integrate with DigiVol, however if DigiVol is returning crowdsourced data to the supplying institutions, and those institutions are Trove partners then this material is being contributed to Trove.</p> <p>Any opportunities here would require strategic decisions to be made.</p>
<p>Integrating with research computing services would enable pre-processing of multimodal materials to extract salient features using advanced analytics that require high performance computing and make them readily available to researchers (and to the public).</p>	<p>This is likely covered by previous points regarding data extracts from Trove, and re-contributing any data sets generated. As such it is on the list of things that can be investigated</p>

<p>A non-programmatic way of getting rectangular transcribed data would be welcome (e.g. using the OpenRefine webscraping capacity, etc.).</p>	<p>Added to the list of things to be investigated</p>
<p>Trove could prepare some curated subsets of the archive with undertakings about coverage and quality, e.g. all a given newspaper title for a given span of years with 95% OCR accuracy. The emphasis would be on shapely data sets rather than flat-out new acquisitions.</p>	<p>This could be achieved by collection features, which can then also be extended as items that meet the requirements are added. Added to the list of things to be investigated</p>
<p>Trove could report sample OCR error rates for categories of sources.</p>	<p>This is a tricky one, and is dependent on a range of factors, however it may be achievable on a broad level Added to list for Help updates</p>
<p>Clean full text in well thought-out segmentation with metadata for download might be a priority</p>	<p>I think some further information about exactly what is meant here is required. Added to list for further investigation</p>
<p>Trove could set up comprehensive citation options, e.g. a widget on each page to give a citation which the user could copy.</p>	<p>Although this sounds good in theory, Trove is limited by the metadata available for each option. Still, improving citations is something to be investigated further</p>
<p>The API should match the website functionality exactly to keep things simple, remembering the beginner API user as well as the power API user.</p>	<p>Added for further investigation</p>
<p>To improve searches and for other purposes Trove could run Named Entity Recognition on all materials</p>	<p>Named Entity Recognition is run across digitised journals and books as article-level and full-text indexed records are loaded to Trove. This process extracts Geographic entities only, and uses them to add the necessary information to generate the place facet in the search. This also means that this work is predominately limited to Australian place names. We have not yet had the opportunity to extend this further, and there are ethical concerns around use of Persons, particularly when it comes to historic periodicals and representation of First</p>

	<p>Nations peoples.</p> <p>Additionally, with places it is possible for us to do some automated cleanup work through comparing with Gazetteers and other data, whereas with persons and organisations it is somewhat more difficult to automate.</p> <p>Further investigation into this is something to be considered.</p>
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Summary

After reviewing the feedback that was supplied, it appears that the following points occur relatively frequently:

- 1) Many functions that researchers have mentioned that they want are already available in Trove. As such enhancements to help content and targeted training programs may go some way to helping the researchers
- 2) Access to bulk data, and both raw OCR and Corrected data are desirable
- 3) Ability to download data associated with a search without using the API
- 4) Ability to create a data set, then upload that data set as a new resource
- 5) Ability to perform some functions currently limited to the API through the Trove interface.
- 6) Review citations, and provide more information about how these are created.

There are a few other things that came up, but these are the ones that stood out to me.

Trove response to researcher feedback

Suggestion/Feedback	Trove response
Bring the web interface and main public API back into sync, so that researchers can easily transfer queries between the two.	This has been added to the list of things for investigation
Expand the metadata available for digitised resources other than newspapers.	Metadata for non-newspapers digitised content is stored separately to Trove, and making this data available in a more detailed form may not be possible.
Standardise the delivery of text, images, and PDFs and provide download links through the API.	As per the above, the non-newspapers digitised content is stored separately to Trove and this may not be possible.
Provide an option to exclude search results in tags and comments	The fulltext index (described in the constructing search pages) does not search tags and comments Added to list of items to be included in a help update Return of this option to Advanced Search added to list of items for investigation
Finally add the People & Organisations data to the main API.	This has been added to the list of things for investigation
Improve web archives CDX API	The web archives API mentioned here is not officially supported by the National Library/Trove. Changes to the existing API being used and/or an official API for the web archives are not currently likely
Provide new data sources for web archives analysis.	See above
Provide a Write API for annotations.	This is unlikely to be possible within IT security requirements.
Provide historical statistics on Trove resources.	These were removed for various reasons, including resource limitations and low usage
Reassess key authentication and account limits.	Added for investigation in future
Unbreak Zotero integration	Added for investigation in future
Provide useful page metadata	Added for investigation in future

Explore annotation frameworks	Unlikely to be possible within IT security requirements.
Obviously any discussion of new tools or interfaces needs to start by looking at what's already available. This is difficult when the NLA won't even link to existing resources such as the GLAM Workbench. Sharing information about existing tools needs to be the starting point from which to plan investment in the Trove Researcher Platform	Covered in comments on roundtable.
The newspaper endpoint returns both newspaper and gazette titles, even though there's a separate gazette endpoint	Recorded as a bug for investigation
The list zone has recurring problems. At the moment it's impossible to harvest a complete set of Trove lists.	Recorded as a bug for investigation

Suggestion/Feedback	Trove response
Recommendation 1. Establish an app registry I'd recommend the Platform establish a registry of Trove-client apps, in which the URL of the app is stored along with rich metadata describing the app, its developer, its purpose, the platform on which it runs, documentation, configuration options, etc. this registry should be exposed via a Trove App Registry API in the first instance, providing search, update, create and delete functions, and an app should be built as a client of this Registry API, providing a user interface for researchers. The Registry app should itself be registered in the registry. Registry users should be able to create their own "instances" of any registered app, with their own set of configuration options. When they launch their instance, the registry should pass the configuration data to the app as a parameter in the app's URL.	This aligns with other comments regarding sharing of tools and has been covered elsewhere
Recommendation 2. Include code libraries in the App Registry	The core of this is very similar to the comment above, and has been covered elsewhere with sharing of tools

<p>A code library shares many of the features of an actual app: a location on the web, a language or runtime environment, functional description, author, copyright terms, etc. The App Registry should include code libraries as well as apps, to allow researcher-developers to share their libraries, and to find useful libraries produced by other developers which they can reuse in their own apps.</p>	
<p>Recommendation 3. Run app-hosting platforms where there is clear benefit to researchers Potentially, such locally-hosted app platforms could be customised to better facilitate their use with Trove’s API, or to improve usability for specifically research purposes rather than their previous generic purpose.</p>	<p>Hosting third-party apps within Trove is unlikely to meet IT security requirements</p>
<p>Recommendation 4. Revise existing APIs and documentation There are several different APIs within Trove’s API system, and they sometimes seem to differ for purely historical rather than logical reasons. A review of the existing APIs, to better align their data structures and access methods, would be a good basis for further development. API documentation should be written as interactive notebooks, allowing users to experimentally invoke an API while reading the documentation for that API.</p>	<p>Review of the existing Trove APIs and API documentation has been added for further investigation</p>
<p>Recommendation 5. Use REST-style identifiers in the APIs I’d also recommend adopting a REST-style for identifiers in the API; where a call to the Trove API returns identifiers of other objects, those identifiers should be returned in the form of HTTP URIs which can be used directly, rather than as tokens which have to added as a parameter to another URI; or if it does makes sense for the API client application to assemble new query URIs from parts, the assembly instructions should be included in the API response, in the form of a “URI Template”.</p>	<p>Where partners have provided a link to an object, this link is made available in the API. Where identifiers are not URIs they may not be easily resolvable to a URI. Making this possible within the current infrastructure is unlikely.</p>
<p>Recommendation 6. Relax authentication requirements</p>	<p>Added for investigation in future</p>

<p>I'd also recommend dropping the strict authentication requirement for the API. Rather than requiring all requests to provide an API key, the API should just impose stricter usage limits (e.g. number of requests per minute) on unauthenticated requests.</p>	
<p>Recommendation 7. Allow authorization via an HTTP header It should also be possible for an API client to submit its API key using an HTTP header, ideally as a Bearer token in an HTTP Authorization request header, rather than only as a URL parameter. This allows API URLs to be published without the risk of exposing credentials embedded in the API.</p>	<p>Added for future investigation</p>
<p>Recommendation 8. Provide output in CSV format I recommend adding CSV as an additional data format for all API responses. This could be implemented easily using a front-end HTTP proxy on top the existing API, and it would provide a considerable head start for many API users for whom converting the data to CSV is a first step towards analysing it in a spreadsheet app, or importing it into a relational database.</p>	<p>Added for future investigation</p>
<p>Recommendation 9. Provide IIIF interoperability I recommend adding support for IIIF where suitable. API search results, lists, etc, could be published as IIIF Collection resources, and newspaper and OCR content could be published as IIIF Manifests with Annotations. This would allow Trove content to be surfaced, in its full richness and retaining all its intellectual context, in generic IIIF tools such as Mirador and UniversalViewer.</p>	<p>Added for future investigation</p>

Other Tool wishlists

Suggestion/Feedback	Trove Response
<p>The functional goal would be to establish an Advanced Search while in one 'category' of Trove and to then either switch to another category to search the same query OR to be able to select</p>	<p>This is currently possible through using the categories at the top of the search results. Flagged for a help revision</p>

<p>more than one category during an Advanced Search.</p>	
<p>As Tim notes, the data is somewhere. It would be great if the API could offer the ability to search across categories for place of publication – could this be part of a larger geo-search functionality in Trove? Being able to search by year of publication/creation across categories too. Could the information in the search include ownership of media, as Tim suggests, showing the parent/child relationships? Again, could this be part of a larger geo-search function – a mapping of ownership?</p>	<p>Added for future investigation</p>
<p>Agreed, and I wonder if this again could be worked into a geo-search function that draws results from across the categories and can be searched by place name – drawn either from content, from the description, from place of publication and from user tags.</p>	<p>Added for future investigation</p>
<p>Interface with similar research resources, principally (but not only) with the English-speaking world eg British Newspaper Archive (UK), Papers Past (NZ)</p>	<p>It is unclear how this interface would work, as each system has different underlying data structures and differing business models. Providing links out to these services is achievable through a help update</p>
<p>Embrace private research collections of potentially national, even international, interest</p>	<p>This is covered through options mentioned at the roundtables around sharing data back to Trove.</p>
<p>Partial reconstruction of “lost” Australian newspapers and magazines by harvesting extracts from these “lost” publications that were published in other, contemporary Australian (and often in UK and New Zealand newspapers, and occasionally US newspapers) and “reverse engineer” a partial recreation of the original newspaper.</p>	<p>Should someone wish to do this we would be able to load the data back into Trove. Covered in previous options regarding sharing data back to Trove</p>
<p>Partial reconstruction of “lost” Australian census data. The United States has undertaken a census of its citizens every 10 years since 1791. The United Kingdom has undertaken a census of its citizens every 10 years since 1841. Australia has</p>	<p>Covered under loading data back into Trove.</p>

<p>only undertaken a census of its citizens, at a national level, since 1901 and, the original census data, once aggregated, was not retained. Australian colonial (pre-1901) censi were infrequent and far from comprehensive.</p>	
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Mark Raadgever
National Library of Australia

7. APPENDIX TWO

Trove researcher panel

Professor Paul Arthur, Edith Cowan University

Dr Tully Barnett, Flinders University

Associate Professor Helen Caple, UNSW

Professor Emeritus Hugh Craig, University of Newcastle

Ms Claudia Funder, Arts Centre Melbourne

Ms Fiona Gatt, Professional Historians Association of Victoria

Professor Michael Haugh, University of Queensland

Dr Amanda Lawrence, RMIT

Mr Levi Murray, Melbourne, Project Manager, Supporting Indigenous Research Capability

Professor Melanie Nolan, ANU

Dr Mark St Leon, Retired

Associate Professor Tim Sherratt, University of Canberra

Dr Ruth Singer, University of Melbourne

Dr Yorick Smaal, Griffith University

Professor Benjamin Smith, University of Western Australia

Dr Leonard Smith, ANU

Associate Professor Adela Sobotkova, University of Aarhus

Associate Professor Jason Stoessel, UNE

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Australian Research Data Commons

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